

The identification of highly cited researchers in literature databases: How are different approaches to identify these researchers able to capture Nobel laureates?

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For many years, Clarivate has used publication and citation data to identify exceptional researchers – highly cited researchers (HCRs). HCRs can be defined differently; the approach of Clarivate is one possibility among several others. For example, HCRs can be identified by considering field-normalized citation rates or absolute numbers of citations; inclusion or exclusion of self-citations; and all authors, only corresponding authors or only first authors. In this study, we are interested in the question of how the different approaches (variants) are able to identify Nobel laureates. Do the different HCRs lists contain a similar number of laureates, and what are the reasons for different results? Our findings show that the different variants of defining HCRs lead to very different representations of Nobel laureates in the identified sample.

1. Introduction

Once in 2001 and annually since 2014, Clarivate (and the former Thomson Reuters) has used publication and citation data to identify exceptional researchers – highly cited researchers (HCRs) – in nearly all disciplines. The purpose of Clarivate with the analysis of highly cited papers is “to recognize scientists and social scientists with community-wide influence” (Szomszor, Pendlebury, & Adams, 2020, p. 1124). The ranking list of HCRs worldwide is annually published at <https://clarivate.com/highly-cited-researchers/>. Although the list of HCRs is freely available, the method for identifying HCRs is not completely transparent. The disadvantage of the intransparency is that other researchers than researchers at Clarivate cannot produce the same list although they may have the same data. The advantage is – as David Pendlebury from Clarivate in a personal communication outlined – that it is more difficult for researchers to game the method for producing the list.

The annual publication of the HCRs list is associated with high public attention (which can be observed, e.g., on Twitter, see da Silva & Bernes, 2018), and the institutional number of HCRs is a regularly used indicator in the well-known Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU, see <https://www.shanghairanking.com>). HCRs can be defined differently; the approach of Clarivate is one possibility among several others. HCRs can be identified by considering field-normalized citation rates or absolute numbers of citations; inclusion or exclusion of self-citations; full counting or fractional counting of publications; all authors, only corresponding authors or only first authors; short, long or varying citation windows; and short or long publication periods. In this study, we are interested in the question of how the different approaches (variants) are able to identify Nobel laureates. Do the different HCRs lists contain a similar number of laureates, and what are the reasons for possible different results? Since both awards (being a HCR and receiving a Nobel prize) focus on exceptional researchers, we generally expected high convergence. With our research questions, we contribute to the topic “Practices of evaluation and assessment” of the Science and Technology Indicators (STI) 2024 conference.

2. Datasets used

As a data source for our bibliometric analyses, we used Scopus raw data in the form of a snapshot from the end of April 2021, covering all publications up to the cohort of the publication year 2020. We replicated Clarivate's HCR approach with our own data instead of employing existing HCRs lists as they are annually published by Clarivate. The use of Scopus is beneficial for the purpose of identifying HCRs as an author disambiguation (AU-ID) as well as an institutional disambiguation (AFF-ID) is provided by Scopus at a global scale.

We used five different approaches to identify HCRs in the Scopus database – an approximation to the Clarivate method and four alternative implementations. For the four approaches, we excluded self-citations throughout the analyses and used a 3-year citation window. We identified HCRs on an annual basis for the period 2010 until 2018. We excluded more recent years to ensure the 3-year citation window for every paper (at the time collecting the data). We restricted any selection and analysis to substantial items (article, letter, note, and review) without considering document types such as meeting abstracts or book reviews. As field-classification schema for the normalization of citation counts, we used OECD's¹ Fields of Science and Technology (FOS) (Stahlschmidt & Stephen, 2020).

We identified Nobel laureates from the areas of physics, chemistry, medicine, and economics in the various HCRs lists. For this purpose, we identified the author profiles in our Scopus dataset of all laureates since the year 1985.

3. Five approaches for identifying highly cited researchers

In this study, we compared five approaches (variants) for identifying HCRs:

Variant-0 represents an approximation to Clarivate's approach. This means, we restricted the identification of HCRs to the authors who have published the top-1% of highly cited papers per field. Variant-0 led to a total HCRs list of 14,349 authors for the period 2010 to 2018. This number equals a share of 0.07% of all distinct authors in the period (based on distinct author IDs in Scopus). 5,342 authors entered the list via the field-specific calculations and 9,007 via the cross-field calculations. The 5,342 authors have had a substantial influence in one field, the 9,007 authors have had this influence in several fields.

The second approach (*Variant-1*) follows a slightly different procedure than the approach by Clarivate: instead of searching for HCRs only in the set of the 1% highly cited papers, we calculated the absolute citation numbers of each author for each publication year and field, based on all publications in the database. This approach only focuses on the number of citations, independent of the number of published papers. While we started with about 1 million authors in Variant-0, of which we selected the HCRs, Variant-1 started from all about 20 million authors in the period 2010 to 2018. The reasoning behind the use of this approach for identifying HCRs is the emphasis of high individual visibility: Variant-1 interprets the term "highly cited" as most often cited in absolute and not in relative terms (i.e., per paper published as in Variant-0). In each year of our observation period, all authors in a field with at least the same number of citations like the one at the 1%-margin joined the HCRs list. This procedure led to slightly higher shares of HCRs than 1%, namely (1) between 1.5% and 1.6% of the author population in each individual year, and (2) 2.1% of all authors in the observation period from 2010 to 2018. This "full" list of HCRs included 318,913 authors. This is a substantially higher number of HCRs than we received with Variant-0.

The third approach – *Variant-2* – is identical to Variant-1. The only difference is that we applied fractional instead of full counting of citations according to the number of authors. In other words, all authors of a paper share the number of received citations. The top-1% of authors per

¹ see <https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/38235147.pdf>. The assignment of the classes to the FOS can be requested from the authors.

field entered the list: any author with the same number of fractional citations was considered above the 1%-margin (including the authors at the 1%-margin). Variant-2 led to a slightly lower HCRs number than Variant-1: 313,475 authors represent 2.0% of all authors in the period from 2010 to 2018. On a year-by-year basis, we found an almost constant rate of 1.5% among the authors, increasing from about 46,000 to 77,000 between 2010 and 2018. The advantage of Variant-2 (compared to Variant-1) is that each citation is counted only once. Its disadvantages may be that (1) all authors are treated equally in any group of authors, and (2) highly cited publications with large numbers of authors counted with low citation impact. Especially the first disadvantage led to our third variation – Variant-3.

Variant-3 – the fourth approach – could be called “the corresponding author takes it all” variant. The variant is based on the fact that the corresponding author is the main contributor to a paper (and most of the co-authors have only limited contributions) (de Moya-Anegón, Guerrero-Bote, Bornmann, & Moed, 2013). To identify HCRs, we took the top-1% of corresponding authors in terms of total citation counts. Total citation counts are (again) defined as the number of citations that all papers of a particular author receive. The advantages of the focus on the corresponding author are obvious: all citations and all publications are counted only for one (the main) author. The assumption that the corresponding author makes a considerable contribution to a publication is evident (de Moya-Anegón et al., 2013). The most important disadvantage is the ignorance of any other authors than the corresponding author and the differences in disciplinary or institutional habits of corresponding authorships. In total, the Variant-3 approach for identifying HCR led to 94,415 (corresponding) authors in the period from 2010 to 2018. This number represents 2.0% of all corresponding authors in the considered period and 0.6% of all authors.

The fifth approach (*Variant-4*) is based on the list of authors from the standardized citation indicators database provided by Ioannidis and co-authors (Ioannidis, Baas, Klavans, & Boyack, 2019; Ioannidis, Boyack, & Baas, 2020; Ioannidis, Klavans, & Boyack, 2016). The authors created a publicly available database of influential scientists that includes standardized information on several indicators and a composite indicator. The first version of the list was published in 2016. Updates have been published in 2019 and in 2020 including the top 100,000 authors. Ioannidis and co-authors (Ioannidis et al., 2019; Ioannidis et al., 2020; Ioannidis et al., 2016) used the following indicators: 1) citation score (field-normalized), 2) h-index, 3) adjusted h-index (Schreiber’s h-index), 4) citations to single-authored papers, 5) single- or first-authored papers, 6) citations to single-, first- or last-authored papers. These six indicators were used for the selection of top authors. In addition, they provided an equally weighted composite index of normalized (0, 1; based on the maximum value of each indicator) scores after log-transformation. In their 2020 paper, the authors offer rankings of top 100,000 authors (considering citation impact with and without self-citations) as well as career-long citations versus single-year-citations (citations in Scopus received in 2019) in 22 fields and 176 sub-fields (of the Scopus ASJC). Of the different lists from Ioannidis et al. (2020), we decided to employ the career-long list of authors that is based on indicators calculated without self-citations (since it corresponds best to the lists based on the other variants for identifying HCRs). We selected the top 100,000 authors of this list. However, to make it comparable to the other variants applied in this study, we focused on authors for whom the last year of publication was 2010 or later. This left us with a list of 94,364 authors, who account for about 0.6% of all (worldwide) authors publishing in the period from 2010 to 2018.

4. Results

We found that the absolute numbers and shares of HCRs significantly differ between the five variants. Variant-0 (Clarivate) led to the smallest set of HCRs with $n = 14,349$ and a share of 0.09% of all authors in the period from 2010 to 2018. Variant-1 resulted in the largest list of

HCRs in absolute and relative terms (318,913 and 2.0%). This approach takes the total number of citations gathered by the papers of the top 1% authors per field and year into account. Variant-2 (fractional counting of citations) led to a slightly smaller list than Variant-1 with a number of 313,475 authors (2.0% of all authors in the period). The list of HCRs based on the corresponding authors approach (Variant-3) contains more than 94,415 authors who represent 0.6% of all authors and 2.0% of all corresponding authors in the observation period.

Figure 1 displays the shares of identified Nobel laureates in the HCRs lists who have actively published in a particular year. It is evident that Variant-0 is able to identify only about 10% to 13% in the period from 2010 to 2018, while the four other variants are able to cover between 61% and 92%. Variant-4 (the HCR list from Ioannidis and co-authors) performed best in terms of Nobel laureates' coverage. It reaches a constant share of all publishing Nobel laureates per year of about 90%. Variant-2 (fractional counting of total citations) performed second best in this respect (76% to 87%).

Figure 1: Share of publishing Nobel laureates identified by each variant.

Source: Elsevier – Scopus; Fraunhofer ISI calculations.

The results in Figure 1 show that the total coverage of HCRs from the five variants is considerably different, with Variant-0 being most selective. This might explain the low absolute numbers and therefore low shares of laureates in the HCR lists as such. In another analysis, therefore, we took the absolute numbers into account and calculated the share of Nobel laureates among all selected authors (by a variant) in relation to the share of Nobel laureates in all authors in the database. As the results in Figure 2 indicate, the representation of laureates is poorest with respect to Variant-0. The probability of a Nobel laureate to be in the list of HCRs is between 32 and 51 times higher than for any other author to be selected. In case of Variant-3, which performs best in this respect, the same calculations reveal a probability that is between 131 and 196 times higher than for any author to be selected. The other three variants are only slightly above Variant-0 and reach probabilities that vary between 34 and 63 times higher than the average over the period from 2010 to 2018.

Figure 2: Probability of covering Nobel laureates in the HCRs lists produced by each variant.

Note: * The probability is calculated as the share of Nobel laureates in the particular variant over the share of Nobel laureates in the total database in each particular year.

Source: Elsevier – Scopus; Fraunhofer ISI calculations.

5. Discussion

HCRs can be differently identified in the databases: there is no standard definition of HCRs. Depending on the methods used and the perspectives taken, very different HCRs lists can be expected – as the empirical results of our study demonstrate. HCRs can be identified by considering field-normalized citation scores or absolute numbers of citations; inclusion or exclusion of self-citations; full counting or fractional counting of publications; all authors, only corresponding authors or only first authors; short, long or varying citation windows; and short or long publication periods. As we have revealed in this study with five different variants of defining HCRs, the selection among these options has an influence on the sample of selected researchers. Some options have a stronger influence on the outcome than other options, such as the length of the citation window or the focus on all authors versus on only the corresponding author. The user of HCRs lists should always be aware of the influence these options have on the final lists of researchers. For recruitment processes, e.g., especially the HCRs list that is based on corresponding authors may be relevant, since the list focuses on the main actors in a particular research project.

We investigated in this study whether the various lists of HCRs contain Nobel laureates. The results by Li, Yin, Fortunato, and Wang (2020) show that “Nobel laureates were energetic producers from the outset, publishing almost twice as many papers as scientists in our comparison group ... Yet, compared with this productivity difference, more impressive is the gap in impact. Indeed, the future laureates had a more than sixfold increase over the comparison group in terms of the rate of publishing hit papers, defined as papers in the top 1%”. Thus, one can expect that many Nobel laureates are among the identified HCRs. Our findings show that the different implementations of HCRs lead to very different representations of Nobel laureates in the identified sample. The extremes in this respect were the variants suggested by Clarivate (Variant-0), which only covered about 10% of the publishing laureates, in contrast to the approach suggested by Ioannidis and co-authors. Their approach covered about 90% of the

publishing laureates. Beyond the mere coverage, we were also able to show that the probability of a Nobel laureate to be represented in the list of HCRs is much higher in Variant-3, which focuses on corresponding authors only. A focus on corresponding authors seems to be able to offer a selective set of authors, but at the same time probably capture highly reputable (and very active) researchers.

Open science practices

The data underlying this study is not openly accessible. The Scopus raw data is subject to a licensing contract. The scripts for the statistical analyses applied as well as the scripts for running the different variants for identifying HCRs are available from the authors upon request.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: LB; Data curation: SG; Formal Analysis: SG; Investigation: RF, SG; Methodology: RF, SG; Project administration: RF; Visualization: RF, SG; Writing – original draft: LB, RF, SG; Writing – review & editing: LB, RF, SG.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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